

Investigate the Relationship of Charismatic Leadership and Ocb: Examining the Role of Stressors and Strains

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Abstract

the aimed of this study was evaluated the relationship of charismatic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior and also found the mediating effect of follower's strains and job stressors on charismatic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior. This study has supported our hypothesis. The area of this study was banking sector, data was collected in self-administrated way through questionnaire from the 144 employees working in banks our response rate was 72%. IBM SPSS 20 software was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis has been used to analyze the data.

Key words: *charismatic leadership, organizational citizenship behavior, strains, stressors, banking sector, District Gujrat*

1. Introduction

Organizations have main focus is to increase the financial performance and for this purpose they put almost all the effort on it. Human capital like managers or leaders and employees are the key factor of the success and failure of the organization. The current economic era has defined by the idea of a "new normal". In this era organizations need the leader who bring the change and also motivate the employee in order to contribute towards the successful change. With respect to the contemporary leadership theory, charismatic leaders are good for organizational change. Charismatic leader can be define as ability to inspire the followers through personal behavior, traits, qualities like always ready for change in any situation (Rayton & Yalabik, 2014)

The positive outcomes of charismatic leadership are good employee's performance and job satisfaction. Prior researches have empirically proved that OCB enhance the organizational performance in several organizational setting. OCB can also be called as extra work related behaviors like employee perform extra work which is not prescribed in job description (Boerner, Dutschke, & Wied, 2008). There are some key points of organizational citizenship behaviors are collaboration with peers, regularity or time keeping, perform some extra roles which are not included in job description, help the other volunteering, and positively representative of the organization (Khan, Ghouri, & Awang, 2013). It helps the manager or leader to be focus on improving the organizational performance. OCB also has negative consequences job stress is one of them.

Leadership style of supervisors become the cause of job stress depend on organizational climate. Strain are basically comes from different stressors. These stressors are related with the job, organization, or work environment, family relationship whereas strains are negative reactions or outcomes an employee experiences due to stressor. The most commonly stressors are the role stressor that may occur because of role ambiguity, role conflict, over workload (Loo, 2013; Pookaiyaudom, 2015). A high level of stress among employees may leads towards a high level of strain. Strain may appear in the form certain reaction such as psychological, physical and behavioral reaction.

The reason behind this study is to explore charismatic leadership in work stress environment and implement the concept of OCB in the banking sector.

1.1. Problem Statement

Pakistan banking sector is facing many problems that's why their employees need more training, guidance and cooperation with other staff to fulfill the tasks. Meanwhile, employees of banking sector are facing burden because of work overload which is the demand of the employer/ supervisor like the timing of banks is from 9am to 5pm in Pakistan but, there is no time limit so employees have to perform their work after it's off time. This condition becomes the cause of stress. This research will analyze how the bank managers implement the concept of organizational citizenship behavior in stressful work environment.

1.2. Objective of the Study

Main Objective

Main objective of this study is to examine the employees extra role behaviors in stress full environment and also investigate the role of charismatic leader in enhancing the follower's OCB in stressful environment.

Sub Objective

- To find out the relationship between charismatic leadership and OCB
- To find out the mediating role of follower's strain between charismatic leadership and OCB
- To find out the mediating role of job stressors between charismatic leadership and OCB

1.3. Significance of the Study

A lot of studies have showed the relationship of charismatic leadership and OCB but a few has taken the combination of such variables like charismatic leadership as an independent variable, OCB as a dependent variable, Follower strain and stressors as a mediate variables. Here, researchers try to conduct the research on banking sector of Pakistan so that significant contribution could be made in this regard. This study can be proved as productive for managers and staff as well. So that they can develop certain policies and strategies which ultimately improve the employees performances and make a strong bonding between leader and followers.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Charismatic Leadership (CL)

Leaders are the owners who have checked on the every aspect of business operations. Max Weber defined the charismatic leadership in 1947 according to him “charismatic leadership style is based on a form of heroism or extreme of character, almost of divine origin”. Mumford, Connelly, & Gaddis stated that Effective leadership could be explain better in term of team building, motivation and inspiration with the help of charismatic leadership style (Mumford, Connelly, & Gaddis, 2003). In addition, Charismatic leadership has focused on collective identification as well as it emphasis on how they communicate the follower about the high performance expectation (Ehrhart & Klein, 2001). It has also emphasis on to communicate with followers on an emotional level including some personality traits in order to gain the follower’s trust (Miles, Borman, Spector, & Fox, 2002). Low role conflict and ambiguity, high motivation, self-confident, positive attitude towards the work are the results from followers who have experienced the charismatic leadership (Jacobsen, House, 2001).

2.2. Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

OCB defined as “behavior that goes beyond the basic requirements of the job, behavior is to a large extent discretionary, and behavior is of benefit to the organization”. Lee and Allen also define the OCBs as “OCBs are employee behaviors that, although not critical to the task or job, serve to facilitate organizational functioning”. Gautam, Dick, Wagner, Upadhyay, and Davis stated that the organizational citizenship differ from culture to culture and organization to organization (Gautam, Dick, Wagner, Upadhyay, & Davis, 2005). Chaitanya and Tripathi suggested the dimensions of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors like Altruism, Courtesy, Civic Sense, Sportsmanship and Perception of Organization towards OCB (Chaitanya & Tripathi, 2001) Employees who involve in organizational citizenship behavior perform better as compare to other (Miles, Borman, Spector, & Fox, 2002; Julian, Catherine, & Kelloway, 2002). This could be happened because of employees who engage in OCB may accept extra duties and responsibilities at work also they help the subordinates in their work (Julian, Catherine, & Kelloway, 2002).

2.3. Charismatic leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

When a leader understands the feeling and need of followers and set the goals and strategies those encourage them that show employee’s good citizenship behavior. It is proved that Charismatic leadership has a significantly positive relationship with OCB. Charismatic leadership act as a helper for employees to build a positive, strong and helpful relationship in which they are willing to help each other (Zehir et al., 2014). Workers who have experienced the charismatic leadership may likely to spend more power mean energy for the organization betterment and defining their role as well (Boerner, Dutschke, & Wied, 2008). The owners and the managers should be familiar with the effective leadership styles and behaviors also their effects on organizational citizenship behavior. Naveed, Arsalan and Marinah stated that leadership effectiveness may become the cause of good employee’s citizenship that would increase the performance at organizational level. Researcher has proved that all leadership styles have a significant and strong relationship with OCB (Khan, Ghouri, & Awang, 2013). From a previous study, researchers have empirically proved the relationship between CL and ocb. Consequently, CL has a positive relation with ocb (Ikram Ul Haq , Farooqi, & Ahmad , 2016). Meredith, Roberson & Oriol found out that more involvement of workers in their work and promote the organizational citizenship effectively could happened in the presence of charismatic supervisor (Roberson & Oriol, 2010). Prior studies empirically proved that CL has a significant positive effect on OCB

H₁: There is positive relationship between charismatic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior.

2.4. Role of Strains and stressors

Kevin Loo stated that stressors are the role stressors like role ambiguity, role conflict and role overload. These stressors roles are the big reason behind the follower’s strain. When the information is to be communicates the role holder is unclear become the cause of role ambiguity while role information is clear but role holder received it from some conflicting source may occur role conflict (Gopinathana & Raman, 2015; Loo, 2013). In case, if role holder received clear and non-conflicting information but the role demands more resources, role overload may occur (Loo, 2013). Different researchers have stated that role ambiguity& role conflict were negatively linked with organizational commitment, job satisfaction, performance, involvement and were positively linked with anxiety, tension, turnover intentions and emotional fatigue , physical symptoms (Nixon et al., 2011). Workload has been linked to various psychological strains like anxiety, frustration, life dissatisfaction and depression. Strain may also appear in the form of

behavioral reactions like absenteeism and turnover (Boerner, Dutschke, & Wied, 2008). Role overload has a direct and significant relationship with psychological strain because performing different task in a tight schedule may increase the job responsibilities which lead to psychological strain. Role conflict and ambiguity has no significant relation with psychological strain (Jdaitawi et al., 2013).

2.5. Charismatic Leadership, OCB, Job Stressors and Follower's Strain

Researchers expected in his study that stressor may reduce the extra role behavior and thus charismatic leader has responsibility to improve the follower's OCB. But they found out that high amount of stressors did show any result on significant impact of charismatic leadership on follower's OCB. Follower strain has negative relationship with the charismatic leadership and OCB (Boerner, Dutschke, & Wied, 2008). In the high stressful situation followers of charismatic leader maintain their performance by showing minimum aggression in behavior (Dvir, Eden, Avolio, Shamir, 202). Researchers have stated negative outcomes from the result of job stressors has direct effect on work aggression, job dissatisfaction and negative emotions (Sandy, et al., 2007; Miles, Borman, Spector, & Fox, 2002). It is suggested by researchers that effective charismatic leadership has negative relationship with harmful workplace behaviors (Sin, 2012). Barling, Loughlin, and Kelloway have found that transformational leadership has negative link with safety accident, charisma is the major element of transformational leadership (Julian, Catherine, & Kelloway, 2002). Job stressors of work overload, organizational constraints, interpersonal conflicts and organizational politics can relate with the OCB. It is empirically proved that there is negative relationship between job stressor & OCB (Brien, 2008) and positive relationship between CL and OCB (Wang, Zhou, & Wen, 2014)

H₂: Follower's strain mediates the relationship of charismatic leadership with organizational citizenship behavior.

H₃: Job stressors mediate the relationship of charismatic leadership with organizational citizenship behavior.

2.6. Conceptual Framework

Charismatic leadership is an independent variable while organizational citizenship behavior is dependent variable. Here stressors and follower's strain act as mediators.

3. Methodology

3.1. Population and Sampling Design

The population of the study included the employees working in banks in Punjab those are registered to State bank of Pakistan and have their branches across the country of Pakistan. These are almost 22 private sector commercial banks.

For our study 200 employees working in the banks have been selected as a sample by use of different sampling techniques in a procedure. The selection of this sample has done by following the process like; Punjab was divided into divisions like Lahore, Gujranwala, Multan, Faisalabad, Sargodha, Jhelum and Gujrat etc. on the basis of geographical location by use of multistage cluster sampling technique. Cluster of Gujranwala division has been selected through simple random sampling. Gujranwala cluster has been divided into district on the basis of geographical location like Gujrat, Sialkot, Gujranwala, Mandi-Baha-ul-din districts etc. through second stage cluster sampling techniques. From the clusters of district, Gujrat district has chosen randomly. Furthermore, one branch of the each bank has chosen randomly from district Gujrat and collected the data from the employees of the selected branch. The banks have almost similar working environment in their all branches, so the data can provide alike results same as to larger geographic area. The sample is selected by keeping in view the time, budget and accessibility constrains

3.2. Sample Size

In order to determine the sample size we have used formula by "Taro Yamni".

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne}$$

n= sample size

N= population

e= marginal error (0.05)

According to formula calculation the sample size of 200 has chosen.

3.3. Data Collection Method

The instrument use for data collection is questionnaire. The questionnaire has two sections. At first it includes demographic information i.e. age, gender, marital status, job position, experience, education and salary while second section consists of variables information. Charismatic leadership was measured by 7 items were taken from (Waldman, G. Ramirez, J. House and Puranam, 2001). Followers' strain was measured by 3- items, Job stressors were measured by using 5- items, Organizational citizenship behavior was measured by 4 items which were taken from (Boerner, Dutschke, & Wied, 2008). Five-point Likert rating scale is use and scale ranging from "strongly disagree" as "1" to "strongly agree" as "5". The questionnaire is to be distributed and filled in a self-administered way.

3.4. Statistical Tool

Descriptive statistics is use to check the level of age, gender, job position, education, tenure and salary. For the internal consistency reliability test of the items, Cronbach's alpha is calculated. In order to check the "relationship between charismatic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior, and mediating effect of follower's strains" IBM SPSS 20 software is use for Regression and correlation to analyze the data. Correlation shows the relationship among variable while regression shows the strength of the relationship.

4. Data analysis

4.1. Descriptive statistics

Response rate of our study was 72%, out of 200 questionnaire we received 144 complete response from the employees of banking sector in district Gujrat. Table A-1 shows that 83 respondents in our study were male (57.6%), 79 were married (54.9%), 63 respondents have bachelor's degree (43.8%), 66 have master (45.8%), 14 have MPhil (9.7%), only one respondent has diplomas (.7%). 13 respondents perform work as a manager (9%), 22 are operational manager (15.3%), 39 are customer service officers (21.5%), 36 are performing their job as a teller (25%), 9 are the accountant (6.3%) and 33 respondent give response on other (22.9%). 25 respondents job tenure is less than 2 years (35.4%), 34 has 3-5 years (23.6%), 19 has 6-10 years (13.2%),40 has more than 10 years (27.8%). 14 respondents have a salary range is less than 15,000 (8.3%), 47 have 16000-25000 (32.6%), 47 have 26000-40000 (32.6%), 22 have 41000-55000 (15.3%) and 16 respondents give the response on more than 55000 salary range (11.1%). Table A-2 shows the mean value of age is 32.56 and SD is 9.345.

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	83	57.6
	female	61	42.4
Marital status	Married	79	54.9
	Unmarried	65	45.1
Education	Bachelor degree	63	43.8
	Master	66	45.8
	MPhil	14	9.7
	Diplomas	1	0.7
Designation	Manager	13	9
	Operational manager	22	15.3
	Customer service officer	39	21.5
	Teller	36	25.6
	Accountant	9	6.3
Tenure	Other	33	22.9
	Less than 2 years	51	35.4
	3-5 years	34	23.6
	6-10 years	19	13.2
Salary	More than 10 years	40	27.5
	Less than 15,000	12	8.3
	15,000-25,000	47	32.6
	26,000-40,000	47	32.6
	41,000-55,000	22	15.3
Above 55,000	16	11.1	

Table A-2:

Age		
N	Mean	S.D
144	32.56	9.345

4.2. Reliability Test

Reliability test is used to measure the strength or consistency of items of variable which are used in data collection. Reliability is measured by using Cronbach’s Alpha. We have checked the reliability by use of Cronbach’s Alpha of the variables collectively and individually as well. Table A-3 shows the value of Cronbach’s Alpha of charismatic leadership, follower’s strain, stressors and organization citizenship behavior were .865 which means our instrument is reliable while in table A-4 values of Cronbach’s Alpha of all variables individually were given.

Table A-3:

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.865	4

Tables A-4:

Reliability Statistics		
Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Charismatic leadership	.864	7
Follower’s strain	.860	3
Job stressors	.737	5
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	.759	4

4.3. Correlation analysis

Table A-5 shows the correlation results which is supported the H1 and showed that there is a positive correlation between CL and OCB (.471**). So the researchers accepted the H1 which is there is positive relationship between CL and OCB.

Table A-5:

Correlation		
	CL	OCB
CL	1	
OCB	.471**	1

4.5. Mediation Analysis

The hypothesis H2 and H3 proposed that job stressors and follower’s strains mediates the relationship of charismatic leadership with organizational citizenship respectively. These hypothesis proved by following the four steps of Baron and Kenny (1986) to check the mediation effect. According to this;

Step 1, charismatic leadership (independent variable) influence the follower’s strain and job stressors (mediate variable) respectively i.e., path a

Step 2, Follower’s strain and job stressors influence the organizational citizenship behavior respectively i.e., path b

Step 3, charismatic leadership influence the organizational citizenship behavior i.e., path c

Step 4, follower’s strain and job stressors reduce the effect of charismatic leadership on organizational citizenship behavior respectively i.e., path c’.

Hypothesis has proved in the following diagram. Hence, H2and H3 of this study is also supported. *The following diagrams show the results of the proposed hypothesis of mediation Hypothesis 2 & 3.*

Note: CL is charismatic leadership, JS is job stressors, OCB is organizational citizenship behavior and FS is followers strain

Above diagram shows that job stressors and follower's strain are the partial mediator. Here *path c'* shows the mediation effect which is less than *path c*.

5. Discussion

In this study it has examined the relationship between CL and OCB. The findings of this study supported the first hypothesis that's charismatic leadership has a strong relationship with OCB. This result is consistent with the previous study (Khan, Ghouri, & Awang, 2013). In the organization, high role of charismatic leader could increase the concept of organizational citizenship behavior. Moreover, the second hypothesis also supported that follower's strains was confirmed as a mediator for the relationship of charismatic leadership and OCB. This result is consistent with the result of (Boerner, Dutschke, & Wied, 2008). Charismatic leadership contributed in decreasing the effect of follower's strain on organizational citizenship behavior. At third, stressor also confirmed as a mediator in the relationship of charismatic leadership and ocb.

Furthermore, in this study researchers have used limited area of stressors and strain and did not cover full range of strains and stressors effect on relationship of charismatic leadership and ocb. Also only on one sector and one city have targeted. For further study a complete form of stressors and strain could be used to check the impact of other styles and behaviors of leadership with OCB.

6. Conclusion

Charismatic leadership acts as an originator for the organizational citizenship behavior. Therefore, mostly employees in banking sector face a lot of stress while doing their job. For this, it should be find that how charismatic leadership plays their role to enhance the organizational citizenship behavior in the presence of strains and stressors. And find the relationship was held between CL and OCB. In our study it is found in case of strains or stressors the relationship between charismatic leadership and ocb differently as compare to in the absence of those.

In our study it had showed stressor reduce the level of ocb of the employees in the organization. Here charismatic leader remove the obstacles, reduce the stress, and provide social support that will increase the intrinsic motivation and enhance the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees. Same as in case of follower's strain, it partially mediates the relationship of CL and ocb. In both cases, charismatic leadership enhances the motivation of the employees, self-efficacy, self-perception of the employees in the organization that will increase the follower's ocb by overcoming the obstacles in the form of strain and stressors.

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Appendix

Mediation analysis: (follower's strain)

Step 1.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.543 ^a	.295	.290	2.83471

a. Predictors: (Constant), CL

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	477.445	1	477.445	59.417	.000 ^b
Residual	1141.049	142	8.036		
Total	1618.493	143			

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

b. Predictors: (Constant), CL

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	8.131	1.017	7.995	.000
CL	.280	.036	.543	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

Step 2.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.290 ^a	.084	.078	6.27592

a. Predictors: (Constant), FS

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	513.453	1	513.453	13.036	.000 ^b
Residual	5592.984	142	39.387		
Total	6106.438	143			

a. Dependent Variable: CL

b. Predictors: (Constant), FS

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	19.336	2.259	8.560	.000
FS	.677	.188	.290	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CL

Step 3.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.322 ^a	.104	.097	2.65832

a. Predictors: (Constant), OCB

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	115.860	1	115.860	16.395	.000 ^b
	Residual	1003.466	142	7.067		
	Total	1119.326	143			

a. Dependent Variable: FS

b. Predictors: (Constant), OCB

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.499	1.064		7.045	.000
	OCB	.268	.066	.322	4.049	.000

a. Dependent Variable: FS

Step 4.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.570 ^a	.324	.315	2.78469

a. Predictors: (Constant), FS, CL

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	525.108	2	262.554	33.858	.000 ^b
	Residual	1093.385	141	7.755		
	Total	1618.493	143			

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

b. Predictors: (Constant), FS, CL

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.335	1.234		5.134	.000
	CL	.223	.037	.491	6.791	.000
	FS	.216	.087	.179	2.479	.014

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

Job Stressor

Step 1

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.271 ^a	.074	.067	6.31138

a. Predictors: (Constant), stressor

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	450.080	1	450.080	11.299	.001 ^b
	Residual	5656.358	142	39.834		
	Total	6106.438	143			

a. Dependent Variable: CL

b. Predictors: (Constant), stressor

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	19.870	2.264		8.778	.000
	stressor	.419	.125	.271	3.361	.001

a. Dependent Variable: CL

Step 2

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.191 ^a	.037	.030	4.168

a. Predictors: (Constant), OCB

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	93.903	1	93.903	5.406	.021 ^b
	Residual	2466.736	142	17.371		
	Total	2560.639	143			

a. Dependent Variable: stressor

b. Predictors: (Constant), OCB

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.857	1.669		8.303	.000
	OCB	.241	.104	.191	2.325	.021

a. Dependent Variable: stressor

Steps 3

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.545 ^a	.297	.287	2.84051

a. Predictors: (Constant), stressor, CL

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	480.834	2	240.417	29.797	.000 ^b
	Residual	1137.659	141	8.069		
	Total	1618.493	143			

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

b. Predictors: (Constant), stressor, CL

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.645	1.265		6.042	.000
	CL	.273	.038	.530	7.228	.000
	stressor	.038	.058	.048	.648	.518

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

Step 4

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.543 ^a	.295	.290	2.83471

a. Predictors: (Constant), CL

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	477.445	1	477.445	59.417	.000 ^b
	Residual	1141.049	142	8.036		
	Total	1618.493	143			

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

b. Predictors: (Constant), CL

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.131	1.017		7.995	.000
	CL	.280	.036	.543	7.708	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OCB

Questionnaire

SECTION A: Demographic information

This questionnaire is about the charismatic leader, follower's strain, stressors and organizational citizenship behavior.

Your age _____

Gender:

Male

Female

Marital Status

Married

Unmarried

Your highest education

- Bachelor degree
- MPhil

- Master degree
- Diplomas

Your current designation

- Manager
- Operational manager
- Customer service officer

- Teller
- Accountant
- Other

Positional Time period:

- Less than 2 year
- 3-5 years

- 6-10 years
- More than 10 years

Salary

- Below 15,000
- 16,000- 25,000
- 26,000-40,000

- 41,000- 55,000
- Above 55,000

Please tick one of the following according to the details given below

SECTION B:

1 = strongly disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = strongly agree

Charismatic Leadership		1	2	3	4	5
1	My supervisor shows determination when accomplishing goals.					
2	I have complete confidence in my supervisor.					
3	My supervisor makes people feel good to be around him/her.					
4	My supervisor communicates high performance expectations.					
5	My supervisor generates respect.					
6	My supervisor transmits a sense of mission.					
7	My supervisor provides a vision of what lies ahead.					
Follower's strain						
8	When I come home from work, I am often too tired to do anything else					
9	I feel exhausted after work.					
10	My job makes me feel worn out at the end of the day.					
Stressors						
11	I have to work under severe time pressure					
12	I have to do physically demanding work					
13	I often cannot finish my assignment because of interruption					
14	I frequently have to do several things at the same time					
15	Small errors can have a strong impact on task accomplishment					
Organizational citizenship behavior						
16	I help others who face heavy workloads					
17	I do not complain in about trivial matter					
18	I try to keep abreast changes within organization					
19	I don't take extra breaks					